

Water Scarcity in Quetta City: A Critical Analysis and Pathways to Sustainability

Najeeb Ullah Sarparah

M.Phil. Scholar at the Department of Disaster Management & Development Studies University of Balochistan Quetta

Dr. Ghulam Murtaza

Associate Professor, Department of Disaster Management and Development Studies, University of Balochistan Quetta

Dr. Muhammad Ashraf

Associate Professor, Department of Disaster Management and Development Studies, University of Balochistan Quetta

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
61-85

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Volume:6, Issue:1, 2026

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

OJS **PKP**
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Abstract

Water shortages in Quetta affect public health, environmental sustainability, and economic stability. Despite an expanding body of hydrological and policy studies, substantial empirical and conceptual gaps remain in understanding water scarcity in Quetta. This study examines the groundwater depletion in Quetta city. A mixed-methods approach analyses groundwater levels, stakeholder perceptions, and water service station operations and roles. The research employs structured questionnaires to gather quantitative data and investigates water service stations regarding their activities, water sources, and the influence on groundwater. A sample of N=153 households is chosen to achieve statistical significance. The sample includes residences from various socioeconomic strata to represent a range of water consumption behaviours, challenges and awareness levels. Four Local government officials, WASA representatives, stakeholders, and community leaders were interviewed using a semi-structured interview design. Quantitative data analysis and thematic analysis to analyse qualitative interview data. The study concludes that awareness is nearly universal, with 88% agreeing that they are aware of groundwater depletion in Quetta. The study showed no association between race, culture, or residence and water saving. Current research indicates that Quetta's regulations and stakeholder activities are failing due to a fragmented operational chain, characterised by the absence of universal licensing, limited metering, infrequent inspections and minimal penalties. A transformation from normative to operational governance is necessary. Important steps include declaring the Quetta Valley a Critical Aquifer Management Zone in accordance with IWRM, instituting well suspensions, and designating priority recharge areas.

Keywords: Water scarcity, groundwater depletion, water consumption behaviours, hydrological policies, Critical Aquifer Management Zone.

Corresponding Author Email:

gmurtaza_80@yahoo.com